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Electrolyte Assessment In The Liver Of *Oryctolagus cuniculus* Intoxicated With Produced Water

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ABSTRACT

This study evaluated the impact of produced water on *Oryctolagus cuniculus* by assessing liver electrolytes, after 30 days of exposure to sublethal concentrations of toxicant in a randomized experiment. After the exposure, a small portion of Liver from experimental animals were collected by dissection, crushed in a ceramic mortar, harmonized with deionized water, and centrifuged for 15 minutes at 3000 rpm. The supernatant was collected in sample bottles for electrolytes assay. The result shows that Na⁺ levels in the liver declined significantly from 145.0±2.0 mmol/L to 108.0±4.36 mmol/L at 20.00 mg/L. While K⁺ fell from 5.10±0.22 to 3.33±0.47 mmol/L. On the other hand, values of Chloride, Calcium and Magnesium were not significant. These findings demonstrated that produced water disrupts liver electrolyte balance in exposed rabbits, thus providing a scientific basis for advocating improved waste management practices and reinforcing environmental protection policies to mitigate the detrimental effects of oil industry effluents.

Keywords: *Oryctolagus cuniculus*, Electrolytes, Produced Water, Sublethal.

INTRODUCTION

Petroleum exploration and production have played a central role in the economic development of many countries, including Nigeria. The Niger Delta region, in particular, has become globally recognized due to its rich deposits of oil and gas, which account for a significant portion of the country's foreign exchange earnings (Ololade & Lajide, 2010). However, alongside these economic benefits, there has been a considerable environmental and public health cost associated with oil and gas activities, especially due to the improper handling and disposal of petroleum by-products such as produced water (Ehirim & Nwankwo, 2010).

Produced water, a major waste stream generated during oil extraction, contains a mixture of organic and inorganic substances, including heavy metals, hydrocarbons, radionuclides, and chemical additives (Orem *et al.*, 2007). When released into the environment without adequate treatment, it can pose serious ecological risks, particularly to aquatic and terrestrial organisms (Nduka & Orisakwe, 2011). The Niger Delta, characterized by its network of rivers, creeks, and wetlands, has been particularly vulnerable to contamination, affecting not only biodiversity but also human health and livelihoods dependent on natural resources (Igwe & Abia, 2006).

This underscores the need for thorough investigation into the toxicological effects of produced water on sentinel organisms such as *Clarias gariepinus* and *Oryctolagus cuniculus*, which serve as models for assessing aquatic and terrestrial environmental health, respectively. Globally, it is estimated that for every

barrel of oil extracted, approximately three barrels of produced water are generated (Khatib & Verbeek, 2003). This makes it the largest waste stream associated with oil production activities.

MATERIALS AND METHOD

A total of twenty-five (25) healthy New Zealand rabbits weighing 1800 g to 2000g per weight were obtained from Kester Farms at Ogboloma, Gbarain Kingdom, Yenagoa, Bayelsa State and used in this present study. Rabbits were transported and put into individual hutches in the animal house of the Department of Biological Sciences, Niger Delta University. Whereas, produced water was collected in a clean container from a Rig site at Imiringi Community, Ogbia Local Government Area, Bayelsa state, Nigeria. Acclimation was carried out following the method described by Inyang, (2008) for 14 days, followed by a trial experiment for another seven (7) days. The sublethal doses for the definitive experiment were eventually obtained from the trial experiment and a completely randomized experimental design was used to expose experimental animals to the test toxicant. The definitive experiment comprised of one control group with four replicates, and three treatment groups of four replicate each. During this period, rabbits were provided with 1.5 L of tap held in metal containers and were fed with poultry feeds daily.

Three concentrations (6.60 mg/L, 13.3 mg/L and 20.0 mg/L) were obtained following the trial test and was used for the main experimental run. The main experimental test lasted for 4 weeks (31days) following a randomized renewal bioassay. At the end of the exposure period, a small portion of the Liver from experimental rabbits were collected by dissection, crushed in a ceramic mortar and harmonized with deionized water. The mixture was centrifuged for 15 minutes at 3000 rpm and the supernatant collected in a sample bottles for electrolytes assay following the method described by Malmstadt and Wine Fordner, (1959).

Statistical Analysis

The data obtained during the experiment was further subjected to statistical analysis using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS), version 20.8 software. The results obtained was then expressed as mean± standard deviation. A one way analysis of Variance was also conducted at $\alpha=0.05$ to determine the significance in the experiment.

RESULT

Table 3.2: Relative activities of electrolytes in the liver of *Oryzotagus cuniculus* exposed to produced water for 30 days

Conc. of Produced water mg/L	K ⁺ (mmol/L)	Na ⁺ (mmol/L)	Cl ⁻ (mmol/L)	Ca ²⁺ (mmol/L)	Mg ²⁺ (mmol/L)
0.00	12.74±0.57 ^b	51.26±0.72 ^b	12.86±0.55 ^c	1.01±0.01 ^{ab}	0.67±0.05 ^b
6.60	14.33±2.47 ^{ab}	63.27±13.96 ^a	19.70±6.32 ^{ab}	1.16±0.50 ^a	0.79±0.06 ^a
13.3	15.30±1.42 ^a	59.23±2.53 ^{ab}	20.39±3.80 ^a	0.91±0.12 ^b	0.77±0.07 ^a
20.0	12.31±0.39 ^b	41.14±3.76 ^c	12.81±0.61 ^c	1.02±0.01 ^{ab}	0.58±0.09 ^c

All data are expressed as mean ± standard deviation using the software programme Statistical Package for Social Sciences version 20.8. Different superscript indicated a significant variation ($p<0.05$) ^a, ^{ab}, ^b, ^c

DISCUSSIONS

These findings highlight significant, dose-related disturbances in hepatic electrolyte homeostasis, indicating hepatocellular dysfunction likely induced by toxic components of PW. Potassium (K⁺) levels increased significantly at 13.3 mg/L (15.30±1.42 mmol/L) compared to the control (12.74±0.57 mmol/L), suggesting membrane destabilization and leakage due to hepatic cell damage (Ezejiofor et al., 2021). The elevated K⁺ may result from impaired Na⁺/K⁺ ATPase activity, a common outcome in hepatotoxicity induced by environmental pollutants (Obiezue et al., 2020).

Sodium (Na^+) concentration peaked at 6.6 mg/L (63.27 ± 13.96 mmol/L) but declined sharply at 20 mg/L (41.14 ± 3.76 mmol/L), indicating alteration of sodium transport mechanisms under increasing toxic stress. This reduction at higher exposure levels may reflect the progressive degeneration of hepatic tissues and altered bile secretion, impairing ionic equilibrium (Otokunefor & Obiukwu, 2019).

Chloride (Cl^-) levels increased significantly at 13.3 mg/L (20.39 ± 3.80 mmol/L), then dropped back to near-control levels at 20 mg/L. Such fluctuations may represent compensatory responses to maintain acid-base balance amidst altered Na^+ and K^+ dynamics (Adeyemi et al., 2022). Calcium (Ca^{2+}) levels remained relatively stable across treatments, with slight variation, while magnesium (Mg^{2+}) increased at moderate exposures but decreased significantly at 20 mg/L (0.58 ± 0.09 mmol/L), suggesting impaired hepatic uptake or excretion at higher toxic doses. These results are consistent with other studies demonstrating hepatic electrolyte derangements following exposure to petroleum derivatives or industrial effluents (Nwankwoala, 2015; Uzoekwe & Oghosanine, 2011). The data confirm that produced water exerts hepatotoxic effects, reflected in disrupted electrolyte distribution and liver dysfunction.

CONCLUSION

This study assessed the physiological impacts of produced water on *Oryzotagus cuniculus* (New Zealand rabbit) following a 31-day exposure period. These findings highlight significant, dose-related disturbances in hepatic electrolyte homeostasis, indicating hepatocellular dysfunction likely induced by toxic components of PW. Comprehensive analyses of serum electrolytes in the liver were conducted to evaluate systemic effects. The findings demonstrated that produced water, even at low concentrations, adversely affected both organisms, with more pronounced disruptions observed at higher concentrations.

Ethical Issues

The authors are aware of ethical issues as stipulated by the laws of the land and thus completely complied with best practices while carrying out this research.

Competing Interest

Authors declare that there is no conflict of interest that would affect the authenticity and originality of this scientific manuscript.

Authors Contribution

All authors of this research made equal imputes both for data collection, analysis and manuscript writing.

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